

BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEM FOR THE EQUATION OF THE TRANSVERSE VIBRATION OF A BEAM

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854545>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 12th April 2023

Accepted: 21th April 2023

Online: 22th April 2023

KEY WORDS

ABSTRACT

Consider the transverse vibrations of a thin beam. The main difference between beam vibrations and transverse string vibrations is that the beam resists bending. Vibrations of a beam clamped at one end are described by the following equation [3]

$$u_{tt} + a^2 u_{xxxx} = 0, \tag{1}$$

(Here $u = u(x, t)$ – beam displacement). Boundary conditions for a given end ($x = 0$)

are the immobility of the beam and the horizontality of the tangent $\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t}(0, t) = 0\right)$, at the free

end ($x = l$) must be zero bending moment $M = -E \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} J$ (E – modulus of elasticity of the beam material, J – moment of inertia of the beam section relative to its horizontal axis) and

tangential force $F = -EJ \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x^3}$. Note that in equation (1) $a^2 = -EJ/\rho S$ (ρ – beam material density, S – beam cross-sectional area).

Consider the following mixed problem:

$$\begin{cases} u_{tt} + a^2 u_{xxxx} = 0, & 0 < x < l, \quad t > 0, \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

$$\begin{cases} u(0, t) = 0, \quad u_x(0, t) = 0, \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

$$\begin{cases} u_{xx}(l, t) = 0, \quad u_{xxx}(l, t) = 0, \quad t \geq 0, \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} u(x, 0) = f(x), \quad u_t(x, 0) = g(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq l. \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

We will solve this problem by the method of separation of variables [1] under the assumption that time-periodic^t beam vibrations. Assuming $u(x,t) = X(x) \cdot T(t)$ and substituting the proposed form of the solution into equation (2), we obtain [2]

$$X(x) \cdot T''(t) + a^2 X^{IV}(x) \cdot T(t) = 0.$$

from this we get following

$$\frac{T''(t)}{a^2 T(t)} = -\frac{X^{IV}(x)}{X(x)} = -\lambda.$$

It's clear that $\lambda > 0$ (for the existence of periodic^t decisions). For function $X(x)$ we obtain the problem of natural oscillations

$$X^{IV}(x) - \lambda X(x) = 0 \tag{5}$$

under boundary conditions

$$X(0) = 0, X'(0) = 0, X''(l) = 0, X'''(x) = 0. \tag{6}$$

The general solution of equation (5) is represented as

$$X(x) = A \operatorname{ch}(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) + B \operatorname{sh}(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) + C \cos(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) + D(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x).$$

From conditions $X(0) = 0, X'(0) = 0$ we find that $A + C = 0, B + D = 0$, this implies

$$X(x) = A \left[\operatorname{ch}(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) - \cos(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) \right] + B \left[\operatorname{sh}(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) - \sin(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) \right].$$

Boundary conditions (6) at the right end of the beam give

$$\begin{cases} A \left[\operatorname{ch}(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) + \cos(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) \right] + B \left[\operatorname{sh}(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) + \sin(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) \right] = 0, \\ A \left[\operatorname{sh}(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) - \sin(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) \right] + B \left[\operatorname{ch}(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) + \cos(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) \right] = 0. \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

Homogeneous system (with respect to unknown A And B) (7) has nontrivial solutions if its determinant is equal to zero:

$$\begin{vmatrix} \operatorname{ch}(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) + \cos(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) & \operatorname{sh}(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) + \sin(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) \\ \operatorname{sh}(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) - \sin(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) & \operatorname{ch}(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) + \cos(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}x) \end{vmatrix} = 0. \tag{8}$$

From equation (8) we obtain an algebraic equation for calculating the eigenvalues tasks

$$\operatorname{sh}^2(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}l) - \sin^2(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}l) = \operatorname{ch}^2(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}l) + 2\operatorname{ch}^2(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}l)\cos^2(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}l) + \cos^2(\sqrt[4]{\lambda}l). \tag{9}$$

Denoting $\mu = \sqrt[4]{\lambda}l$ and using the equality $\operatorname{sh}^2 x + 1 = \operatorname{ch}^2 x$, from equation (9) we find

$$\operatorname{ch}\mu \cdot \cos \mu = -1 \tag{10}$$

This equation can be solved graphically (Fig. 1). The roots of equation (10) are

$$\mu_1 = 1,875; \mu_2 = 4,694; \mu_3 = 7,854; \mu_n \approx \frac{\pi}{2}(2n-1) \text{ at } n > 3.$$

Further, for the function $T(t)$ we have the equation

$$T''(t) + \lambda_n a^2 T(t) = 0.$$

Its general solution is written as

$$T_n(t) = A_n \cos(a\sqrt{\lambda_n}t) + B_n \sin(a\sqrt{\lambda_n}t) = A_n \cos\left(a\frac{\mu_n^2}{l^2}t\right) + B_n \sin\left(a\frac{\mu_n^2}{l^2}t\right),$$

Where A_n And B_n - arbitrary constants.

Consequently, the "atoms" of the solution to problem (2), (3) are formed by the following functions

$$u_n(x,t) = \left[A_n \cos\left(a\frac{\mu_n^2}{l^2}t\right) + B_n \sin\left(a\frac{\mu_n^2}{l^2}t\right) \right] \cdot X_n(x),$$

Where

$$X_n(x) = \frac{(sh\mu_n + \sin\mu_n) \left[ch\left(\frac{\mu_n}{l}x\right) - \cos\left(\frac{\mu_n}{l}x\right) \right]}{sh\mu_n + \sin\mu_n} - \frac{(ch\mu_n + \cos\mu_n) \left[sh\left(\frac{\mu_n}{l}x\right) - \sin\left(\frac{\mu_n}{l}x\right) \right]}{sh\mu_n + \sin\mu_n}.$$

According to the general theory of the Sturm-Liouville problem functions $\{X_n(x)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ form a complete orthogonal system of functions on the interval $[0, l]$. Then the solution of problem (2) - (4) is following

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[A_n \cos\left(a\frac{\mu_n^2}{l^2}t\right) + B_n \sin\left(a\frac{\mu_n^2}{l^2}t\right) \right] \cdot X_n(x),$$

where coefficients A_n And B_n - are determined from the initial conditions by the formulas

$$A_n = \frac{\int_0^l f(x) X_n(x) dx}{\|X_n(x)\|^2}, \quad B_n = \frac{\int_0^l g(x) X_n(x) dx}{a\frac{\mu_n^2}{l} \|X_n(x)\|^2},$$

Where

$$\|X_n(x)\|^2 = \int_0^l X_n^2(x) dx.$$

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